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Socio-Economic Status of Livestock Farmers In Mundhewadi Village of Mangalwedha Tahsil (Solapur District)

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Abstract:

Primary economics activities are major occupation in village of Mundhewadi in Mangalwedha tahsil. In this village majority of peoples are engaged in agriculture. In this situation the livestock are also helps to increase the economic contribution. The prime objective of this research is to study the socio economic status of livestock farmers in this village. For this research 200 livestock farmers of this village were selected. Questionnaires were used to collect the data. As per study in this region majority of the peoples are landless and small land holder and other hand majority of people don't have land for grazing animal which they depend on others field.

Majority of respondents of this region are low income group, less consumption of milk, less production of milk and low income source. In this study region around the 75 percent of respondents were taking fruit crops. Some another is taking cash crops but these crops not useful for cattle. If people use scientific method for raring animals they will improve their socio-economic status.

Keywords: Rural employment, Economic activities, Food and Cash crops, Rural economy, Irrigated Land, GVA etc.

Introduction:

Agriculture plays an important role in Maharashtra as well as India and it is also the largest livelihood provider in rural areas. It also contributes a significant figure to the GDP. Sustainable development should be necessary for holistic rural development, so it will be necessary to increase food security, rural employment and environmentally sustainable technologies. Indian agriculture and allied economic activities witnessed a green, white, blue and a yellow revolution. In the Indian economy agriculture plays vital role. Over 70 percent of the rural householders depend on agriculture as their principal means of livelihood. Gross fixed capital formation in agriculture was 17.7 percent in 2013-14 and it decreased in 2017-18 by 2.5 percent. Contribution of agriculture sector in Indian economy is higher than world's average rate. Gross Value Added (GVA) is estimated at 92.26 lakh crore INR in 2018-19 while agriculture and allied sector shares 15.87 percent. A large numbers of farmers in this region as well as India depend on animal husbandry for their livelihood. The milk dairy subsector occupied an important position in agriculture economy of India, as milk is second largest agriculture commodity in rural area. The dairy sector provides regular employment of many people and they are engaged in this country for production of milk, therefore a large number of unemployment persons have got employment in this sector. Mundhewadi is one of the major jowar production regions in Mangalwedha tahsil of Solapur district (MS). Agriculture is major economic activities in this region. Due to availability of salt water they find some difficulty in production of good

agricultural commodities. One of the challenge in this village is to generate the self-employment opportunity which will be based on their agriculture and milk production. Present investigation is carried out to analyze the socio-economic status of the livestock farmers in this region.

Objectives:

Following are the specific objectives in study region.

1. To find out the socio-economic status of livestock farmers in Mundhewadi village.
2. To examine role of animal husbandry in rural economy.

Study Region:

Mundhewadi is one of the important village in Mangalwedha tahsil in Solapur district

of Maharashtra state, India. It belongs to Desh of Pachim Maharashtra region and Pune division. Mundhewadi is bounded by 17°29'33''N to 17°32'24''N latitudes and 75°30'47''E to 75°34'01''E longitudes. It is bounded by Rahatewadi, Borale, Donaj, Brahmpuri villages and Mangalwedha city. The Mundhewadi village has population of 1245 of which 635 are males while 610 are females as per Population Census 2011. It is located 50 km. from district head quarter and 12 km. from Mangalwedha. It is 498 meters above mean sea level.

Fig No.1

Database And Methodology:

The present study was based on primary and secondary data. The primary data were collected through the questionnaires. For this purpose 200 respondents were selected randomly from the livestock farmers in the Mundhewadi village. Data were also collected from secondary sources of information as like official documents such as records, registrars and reports in Grampanchayat office which were taken by the Talathi and Gramsevak. Also Socio-Economic Abstract of Solapur district were used for data collection.

Result And Discussion:

1. **Land holding Category:** It could be observed from Table No.1, 45.5 percent of farmers are marginal land holder which is highest percent. The landless farmers also found in this village which migrate from other place. They come for survival in this village. Some peoples are engaged in the agriculture worker in the others field. In landless family the women’s are depend on others field and they go to work on daily wages.

Table No.1
Category of farmers according to Land holding

Sr. No.	Category	No. of Farmers	Percentage (%)
1	Landless	27	13.5
2	Marginal Land	91	45.5
3	Medium Land	82	41.0
	Total	200	100.00

Source: Compiled by the Researcher

2. **Income category:** The following table indicates that around the 44 percent of the respondents income is low, because in this village agriculture is major source for income and majority of peoples are agriculture workers. High income agriculture farmers are less than low and medium income farmers. In high income group some family members are also working in other field i.e. driving, teaching, construction etc.

Table No. 2
Income Group of Livestock Farmers

Sr. No.	Distribution	Percentage
1	Low Income	43.50
2	Medium Income	38.00
3	High Income	18.50

Source: Compiled by the Researcher

3. **Family type and Size:** It was found the given table that 71.50 percent livestock farmers are in the nuclear family, the remaining family also found in joint family which indicates the traditional societies plays vital role for this situation. As per family size 1/3 livestock farmers are small family and around the 47.50 percent livestock farmers are medium size family. In large family size around 1/5 livestock farmers are in large family size which will be in joint family. As per study the maximum literate rate is in the small and medium family size.

Table No.3
Family Size and Family Types of Livestock Farmers

Sr. No.	Characteristics	Distribution	Percentage
1	Family Type	Nuclear Family	71.50
		Joint Family	28.50
2	Family Size	Small (1-4)	33.50
		Medium (4-7)	47.50
		Large (>7)	19.00

Source: Compiled by the Researcher

4. Landholding and Cropping pattern: In the table No.4, majority (60.50) of the respondents were holding small acres of rainfed land followed by medium (31.50) and large (8.00). Similarly, majority (78.50) of the livestock farmers had small irrigated land holding and 16.50 percentages of livestock farmers had medium and 5 percentages of livestock farmers had large irrigated land holding. Other hand majority (64.5 percent) of respondents were growing jowar followed by sugarcane (14.5), horsegram (5.5), vegetables (4.5) and pomegranate (3.5). 7.5 percentage respondents other crops also indicates the some are the trying to take another crops.

Table No.4
Land Holding and Cropping Pattern of Livestock Farmers

Sr. No.	Categories	Distribution	Percentage
1	Rainfed Land holding	Small (0-5 Acres)	60.50
		Medium (5-10 Acres)	31.50
		High (> 10 Acres)	8.00
2	Irrigated Land holding	Small (0-2)	78.50
		Medium (2-5)	16.50
		Large (>5)	5.00
3	Types of Crops Grown	Jowar	64.50
		Sugarcane	14.50
		Pomegranate	3.50
		Horsegram	5.50
		Vegetables	4.50
		Others	7.50

Source: Compiled by the Researcher

5. Types of livestock: Due to unavailability of employment in agriculture, many peoples are engaged in the livestock possession for milk production. The following diagram shows that majority of respondents are possessed indigenous breed (39 Percent) followed by Crossbred cattle (25.5), Buffaloes (18.5), Goat (10.5) and sheep (6.5).

Fig No.2
Types of Livestock

6. Milk Production: The following table shows that low (below 10) liter milk production is high level (54.50), followed by medium (36.50) and high (9.00). Also the consumption of milk is low in this village, the respondents found around the fifty percentages and sale of milk also found low (below 2 liter) which also fifty percentages. The given table indicates that the high livestock farmers are engaged in the production of milk but consumption is very low because they want to the milk for the income source.

Table No.5
Milk Production Details of livestock

Sr. No.	Details	Categories (in Liter)	Percentage
1	Milk Production	Low (0-10)	54.50
		Medium (10-20)	36.50
		High (>20)	9.00
2	Milk Consumption	Low (0-2.5)	49.00
		Medium (2.5-5)	36.50
		High (>5)	14.50
3	Sale	Low (0-2)	50.50
		Medium (2-4)	31.50
		High (>4)	18.00

Source: Compiled by the Researcher

Conclusion:

The limited availability of land is major source of grazing land and fodder in this region. So majority of people are trying to take some crops for food which will be beneficial for animal. From the present investigation it has been concluded that the majority of people are take the fruit crops (i.e. jawor) in their field. So it is not possible to use this food for animals in this region, which farmer faced that was availability of green fodder for their cattle's. Due to non-availability of green fodder it becomes difficult to reared dairy animals. Farmers did not get any scientific knowledge or they didn't want to take because they did not rear dairy animal as main money generating source. So it is today's need to aware livestock farmers of this region to rear dairy animal, provide scientific knowledge of livestock and start dairying as a main money generating source therefore it will help to increase their socio-economic status of these peoples. It is difficult that the change the cropping pattern which will be helpful for their cattle's food.

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